

Financial Analysis of the National Response to HIV/AIDS in Tunisia

Working Paper

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19490236>

Final version. January 2012

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Contents	Page
I. Introduction	1
II. The State and Course of HIV/AIDS.....	2
III. The State of Health and the Health System	5
The State of Health.....	5
The Health System	6
Health Financing.....	7
Access to Health Services Across Households.....	8
IV. The National Response to HIV/AIDS.....	9
The Cost of the National Response to HIV/AIDS	10
The (Draft) National Strategic Plan 2012-2016.....	12
V. Projected Costs of National Response to HIV/AIDS.....	14
Projected Course of Epidemic.....	14
Projected Costs of the National Response to HIV/AIDS	15
VI. HIV Incidence and the Costs of the National Response to HIV/AIDS	17
VII. Sustainability of the National Response to HIV/AIDS	19
VIII. Conclusions.....	21
References	22
Appendix: Epidemiological Framework.....	24
Epidemiological Framework	24

Figures

1. HIV prevalence, incidence, and deaths (Reported Cases), 1987-2009.....	3
2. The Course of HIV/AIDS, 1980-2009.....	4
3. Composition of Mortality, 2008	5
4. Health and Demographic Indicators, 1950-2012	6
5. Health Expenditures by Source, 1996-2008.....	8
6. Access to Antiretroviral Treatment, 2001-2009.....	10
7. Available Data on HIV/AIDS Spending.....	10
8. Projected Costs of NSP, 2012-16	13
8. People Living with HIV/AIDS, Ages 15+, 2010-2030.....	15
9. Costs of National Response to HIV/AIDS, 2010-2030	16
10. Costs of National Response to HIV/AIDS, Constant HIV Incidence, 2010-2030	17
11. Costs of One Additional Infection.....	18
12. Fiscal Costs of HIV/AIDS, Commitment Basis	18

Tables

1. Objectives and Operational Targets of National Strategic Plan 2012-2015.....	12
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I. Introduction

Tunisia is currently in the process of finalising its National Strategic Plan for HIV 2012-2015, in the context of a changing global environment for HIV/AIDS financing. The changes in the availability of external funding have direct consequences for Tunisia's HIV/AIDS program. The national response to HIV/AIDS has benefited from a Global Fund grant which substantially contributed to the scaling up of national prevention and treatment programmes in 2007-2011. The planning of the new national strategic plan initially anticipated an application for a new Global Fund grant from the Round 11 call for proposals. The cancellation of the latter means that the national response to HIV/AIDS will need to draw on domestic resources to a much higher extent than anticipated, and adds urgency to an understanding of the financial implications and the sustainability of the national response to HIV/AIDS, and of specific measures and policy alternatives being considered.

The purpose of this report is to provide a financial analysis of the national response to HIV/AIDS, to contribute to the ongoing discussions on the direction and the financing of the national response to HIV/AIDS. The report has been prepared as a "desk review" largely on the basis of publicly available information and key policy documents. Looking ahead, it could contribute to inform the planning and financing of the national response more concretely, e.g., by evaluating specific policy options being considered, and by attuning the analysis more closely with the ongoing policy discussions.

The report is broadly structured in two major parts – a stocktaking of the state of the epidemic, the national response to HIV/AIDS, and the health context; and a forward-looking financial analysis of the national response to HIV/AIDS.

The stocktaking sets out with a discussion of the state and course of the epidemic, and of its contribution to the burden of disease (Section II). This is followed by a discussion of the state of health and the health system, covering the health and demographic context, the structure of the health system, and the financing of health services (Section III). Against this background, Section IV discusses the national response to HIV/AIDS, and summarizes the available information on the costs and the financing of the HIV/AIDS program. The section closes with an a brief review of the key objectives of the emerging new National Strategic Plan for HIV 2012-2015

Sections V to VII contain the forward-looking analysis of the national response to HIV/AIDS. Section V provides projections of the financial costs. As the focus is on the sustainability of the response, and the financial consequences of alternative policies (which materialize only over time), the projections extend beyond the time frame of the new National Strategic Plan (through 2015), and projections are generally reported through 2030. As the outset, the outlook for the HIV epidemic is discussed, building projections based on the estimates of the state of the epidemic so far, and the current state and objectives of the national response. Together with estimates of current HIV/AIDS spending and the costing of the new National Strategic Plan that is being conducted, this forms the basis of the projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS.

Section VI provides an interpretation of the projected financial costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS that is more decision-oriented. The objective is to provide tools that can be used in assessing both small and large policy choices. The section first provides an incremental analysis, estimating the costs of placing one additional person on treatment or – under the policy objectives of the national HIV/AIDS program – the costs which are incurred as a consequence of one additional infection. It is then demonstrated how these techniques can be used to assess the financial consequences of alternative HIV/AIDS policies. The section closes with a preliminary discussion of the link from disease dynamics to the costs incurred by additional infections (or the savings from HIV infections averted).

Section VII pulls together some of the threads from the preceding discussion, and changes the focus to the financing of the national response to HIV/AIDS, addressing the sustainability of HIV/AIDS

spending, placing the costs of HIV/AIDS-related services in a broader health context, and discussing the consequences of the potential drop in external funding.

Sections VIII provides some preliminary conclusions, and discusses the shortcomings of the evidence and the analysis so far in terms of informing the planning of the national response to HIV/AIDS.

II. The State and Course of HIV/AIDS

HIV prevalence in Tunisia is relatively low. According to UNAIDS (2010) estimates, 2,400 people were living with HIV/AIDS in Tunisia in 2009. This implies an HIV prevalence rate of less than 0.05 percent of the population of ages 15-49.¹ About 70 percent (1,700) of the estimated number of adults living with HIV/AIDS are male. Young people account for less than 5 percent of people living with HIV/AIDS.² Higher prevalence rates are reported for a number of sub-populations. A bio-behavioural survey is currently being prepared, preliminary findings suggest higher rates for IDUs (4.8 percent), MSM (13 percent), and a rate of 0.7 percent for people with sexually transmitted diseases (other than HIV/AIDS). As of end-2009, 412 people were receiving treatment, corresponding to a coverage rate of 53 percent.³

The principal data sources on HIV prevalence in the general population are reported HIV cases, for which consistent data, including some characteristics of persons infected (sex, age) and self-reported mode of transmission, are available from 2005-2009. However, reported cases only cover part of the population living with HIV/AIDS, as it frequently is diagnosed only when symptoms become apparent, and some cases are not recorded. For these reasons, and because reported data cover only aspects of the state of the epidemic (e.g., they give only indirect evidence of trends in HIV incidence), primary data are usefully complemented by estimates generated by epidemiological models, such as the estimates published by UNAIDS.

Figure 1 summarizes available data on the number of reported HIV cases and the number of people living with HIV/AIDS. The number of reported cases has increased from 70 in 1987 to 1071 in 2009 (Fig. 1a). The annual number of new reported HIV cases has peaked at 92 in 1994, and fluctuated between 50 and 75 from 1998 to 2009. After 2001, there appears to be a considerable drop in HIV mortality (although the annual figures continue to fluctuate widely), with average annual deaths at 14.6, which is only one-half of the annual number of deaths over the preceding decade. This decline can plausibly be attributed to the impact of antiretroviral treatment, which took off from 2001. As the population expanded by one-third between 1987 and 2009, it is also useful to relate the number of people affected by HIV/AIDS to the size of the population (Fig. 1b). From this perspective, the decline in HIV incidence is more pronounced, but the share of people known to be HIV positive among the total population nevertheless increased steadily.

¹ UNAIDS (2010) reports an HIV prevalence for the population of ages 15-49 of "<0.1 percent." The estimate of 0.05 percent of the population of ages 15-49 was obtained by dividing the number of adults living with HIV/AIDS through the size of this age group, as obtained from UNPD (2011). (This assumes that most adults living with HIV/AIDS are between ages 15 and 49, otherwise the point estimate needs to be adjusted downwards.)

² UNAIDS (2010) provides a rounded point estimate for total number of people living with HIV/AIDS of 2,400 (the same as the rounded estimate for the adult population), implying that the number of young people living with HIV/AIDS is less than 100.

³ Unless stated otherwise, ART coverage rates in this report refer to a CD4 count of 350 as eligibility criterion.

Figure 1. HIV prevalence, incidence, and deaths (Reported Cases), 1987-2009

Apart from changes in the number of new reported HIV cases, there have also been important changes in their composition, which provide insights regarding the dynamics of the HIV epidemic in Tunisia. The share of males among reported HIV cases has tended to decline over the last decade, from around 70 percent to about 60 percent (MSP/PNLS, 2010). More pronounced are the changes in (self-reported mode of transmission). Through 1994, one half of male HIV cases were attributed to injecting drug use, one quarter to “other causes,” (i.e., largely, contaminated blood supplies), 5 percent to homosexual transmission, and 20 percent to heterosexual transmission. The role of “other causes” has dropped steeply (largely as a consequence of improved blood safety) since 1997. The share of homosexual transmission increased more gradually, and averaged 13 percent of reported cases in 2000-2009. The role of IDU fluctuated, but tended to decline and averaged just over one-quarter of total cases in 2005-2009. Consequently, heterosexual transmission now accounts for one-half of new reported HIV cases. For women, heterosexual transmission always was the dominant mode of transmission, although injecting drug use and “other causes” played an important role early on (totalling 40 percent of reported cases before 1995, but only 10 percent after 2000).⁴

Reported HIV cases, together with other survey data (e.g., the number of HIV tests conducted, to allow inferences regarding HIV prevalence and incidence *rates*) are the most important primary data on the state of the HIV epidemic. However, such data may fall short in terms of giving an accurate picture of the state of the epidemic – only a subset of HIV cases are reported, the share of unreported cases may differ across population groups, and survey and test data provide only indirect evidence regarding the underlying trends in HIV incidence, as HIV cases are frequently reported only when a person falls ill, many years after acquiring HIV.⁵

The other approach to gaining insights on the course of the epidemic relies on an epidemiological model, which is parameterized in light of the available data on the state of the epidemic. This allows population level estimates, and is of course a prerequisite for projecting the course of the epidemic. Also, with low HIV prevalence as in Tunisia, actual observations are subject to relatively large fluctuations, which makes interpreting trends difficult. Modelling is a way of smoothing series and identify underlying trends.

The best known of these estimates are those prepared by UNAIDS, reported in UNAIDS (2010a, 2010b, 2010c) for the years 1990 to 2009. An important shortcoming of these estimates is the fact that the reported data are truncated (e.g., a value of “<1,000” instead of a point estimate of 700). The data shown in Figure 2 therefore were constructed based on numbers read off from figures on HIV incidence and the number of people living with HIV included in the UNAIDS/WHO “Epidemiological

⁴ [Note to self: It would be useful to provide some regional context, e.g., by drawing on the analysis by Abu-Raddad and others (2010a, 2010b).]

⁵ About one-half of reported people diagnosed with HIV are diagnosed only at a late stage, when AIDS symptoms are already present (MSP/PNLS, 2010). This means that there is frequently a long time interval between infection and the time a new HIV case is reported.

Factsheet" (UNAIDS/WHO, 2010), and were extended backwards using a simple epidemiological model (similar to the one that is used later in this report).⁶

Figure 2. The Course of HIV/AIDS, 1980-2009

There are at least two important differences between the population-level estimates by UNAIDS and the number of reported cases from MSP/PNLS (2010). First, UNAIDS estimates that about 2,400 people were living with HIV/AIDS in Tunisia at end-2009, whereas MSP/PNLS (2010) report 1,071 people living with HIV as of 2009. These different numbers are consistent, as only a subset of people living with HIV/AIDS (45 percent, according to these data) has been diagnosed and are known to live with HIV/AIDS. (Also recall that a large share of people is diagnosed only when the AIDS symptoms are already present.) Second, UNAIDS estimates that HIV incidence has been increasing steeply in recent years, even though the number of newly reported cases has tended to decline since the mid-1990s (Fig. 1).⁷

To understand the evolving role of HIV/AIDS, it is also necessary to consider the contribution of HIV/AIDS to the burden of disease.⁸ The most comprehensive estimates in this directions are those published by WHO (2011b), providing a snapshot of the causes of mortality for the year 2008 (Figure 3). Life expectancy has reached 74.2 years as of 2009, and infant mortality stood at 20 per 1,000 births (UNPD, 2011). In line with these relatively favourable outcomes,⁹ the majority of deaths are attributed to non-communicable diseases. HIV/AIDS plays a subordinate role, accounting for 0.1 percent of all deaths for the population overall, and 0.4 percent of deaths between ages 15 and 59.

⁶ This was done in three steps: First, the values were read off the figures, and a series for HIV deaths was constructed from the HIV incidence and prevalence data. Second, the series were smoothed to eliminate fluctuations introduced by rounding. Third, from the profile of HIV incidence and prevalence, the series were extended backwards to 1980.

⁷ These discrepancies do not necessarily point to inconsistencies, as reported HIV cases follow actual HIV infections with a lag. However, in light of the scale of the discrepancies (reported cases declining since the mid-1990s, while estimated HIV infections increase more than two-fold since 2002), it would be useful to understand the cause of these discrepancies.

⁸ See also Arfa and Achouri (2008, p. 392-3) for a discussion of the burden of disease, based on earlier WHO estimates for 2002.

⁹ For North Africa (including Tunisia), average life expectancy at birth stood at 69.8 years, and infant mortality at 35.5 per 1,000 births as of 2009.

Figure 3. Composition of Mortality, 2008

III. The State of Health and the Health System

The impact of HIV/AIDS and the response to the epidemic play out against, and are partially shaped by, the state of public health and in the context of the national health system. This has already been recognized in the previous section, which discussed the contribution of HIV/AIDS to the burden of disease. In this section, the attention shifts to the state of the health system, including a discussion of recent health and demographic developments, a description of the health system, and a summary of the state of health financing, both in terms of major categories of funding, and regarding access to health services across households.

The State of Health

Health indicators for Tunisia tend to be the highest in North Africa, and the country is advanced in the health and demographic transition (see also Arfa and Achouri (2008) and WHO (2006)). Figure 3A summarizes health and demographic developments over the last decades. Infant mortality and child mortality have declined steeply, especially between 1970 and 1990 (when infant mortality dropped from 130 per 1,000 births to 40).¹⁰ These developments were also a major factor behind improvements in life expectancy (from 54 in 1970 to 69 in 1990). As a consequence, non-communicable diseases are now the major cause of mortality (compare Fig. 3), and gains in life expectancy have slowed down and are increasingly driven by improved survival at older age. HIV/AIDS does not have a significant impact on life expectancy.¹¹

¹⁰ Arfa and Achouri attribute these developments to the abolition of polygamy since 1956, the implementation of a comprehensive family planning and fertility reduction policy since the early 1960s, and improvements in maternal, child, and reproductive health services (monitoring of pregnancies, immunizations, postnatal care, and birth spacing) since 1960.

¹¹ As a crude approximation, the loss in life expectancy can be calculated by multiplying the contribution of HIV/AIDS to mortality (0.059 percent in 2008, according to WHO (2011b)) with the number of life years lost per AIDS death. WHO (2008) estimates the latter at about 48 years for countries in the Eastern Mediterranean region as of 2004. Multiplying these two figures suggests a loss in life expectancy of about 10 days.

Figure 4. Health and Demographic Indicators, 1950-2012

The decline in child mortality was followed by a decline in fertility (Fig. 3A.2). Whereas the average number of children per woman exceeded 7 until the late 1960s, the fertility rate has declined steadily to 2.0 by 2002, and now is estimated at 1.9, consistent with a long-term population growth rate in the vicinity of zero. Population growth has fluctuated wildly, reflecting three major factors. Until the mid-1970s, migration played a large role, and the decline in outward migration during and after the 1973 oil crisis (while 0.6 percent of the population emigrated in 1972, this rate dropped to close to zero by 1977) has resulted in a steep increase in population growth in this period. Excluding migration, increased survival resulted in an increase in the rate of population growth in the 1950s and early 60s. Largely owing to the drop in fertility, population growth has subsequently dropped from about 2.5 percent annually until 1980 to about 1 percent annually in 2000, and has remained at this level.

As a consequence of the slowdown in population growth, and increased survival, the age structure of the population has changed radically over the last years (figure 3A.3). While the share of the old population (age 60 and older) has grown from 5.9 percent in 1980 to 10.1 percent in 2010, the share of the young population has dropped from over 40 percent until 1985 to 23 percent in 2011. At the same time, Tunisia is undergoing rapid urbanization – the share of the urban population has increased from 51 percent in 1980 to 67 percent in 2010 (UNPD, 2011).¹²

The Health System

Health care is delivered through the public and private sector. The public sector employs 55 percent of all medical personnel, and dominates tertiary care, accounting for 88 percent of all hospital beds (as of 2004, see Arfa and Achouri (2008)). However, the role of the private sector has increased in recent years. Between 1981 and 2004, the number of registered physicians increased from 2,078 (29 per 100,000) to 9,805 (100 per 100,000). Much of this increase occurred in the private sector, the share of which in the number of physicians increased from 32 percent to 47 percent. According to the

¹² According to Arfa and Achouri (2008), the share of the urban population increased from 40 percent in 1996 to 64 percent in 2004. This seems high, and inconsistent with the UNPD data. [Need to resolve inconsistency between sources.]

latest figures published by WHO (2012), the number of physicians has increased further to 12,525 (121 per 100,000) in 2009, and 34,551 nurses and midwives (333 per 100,000) were working in the health system in that year.

The public health sector is organized in three tiers.¹³ A decentralized network of over 2,000 primary health care centres addresses the most immediate health needs. Rural natal care centers and district hospitals (118 hospitals with 2,613 beds) offer medical care, a maternity ward, and basic medical services. There are 34 regional hospitals (5,479 beds) offering specialized medical services, as well as university hospitals and related centres (22 facilities with 8,590 beds) in Tunis, Sousse, Monastir, and Sfax. Additionally, the MSP controls the procurement of drugs through the Central Pharmacy of Tunisia, which is the only institution licensed to import drugs, and sells local and imported products to private wholesalers and public facilities.

Private health services are predominantly delivered through single-practice physicians providing ambulatory care, although inpatient services play an increasing role (WHO, 2006). Additionally, 83 percent of pharmacists and 72 percent of dentists are employed in the private sector (WHO, 2006). Private NGOs do not play a role in Tunisia's health system.

Health Financing

Total health expenditure accounted for 6.2 percent of GDP in 2008 (Fig 4). The public sector (including social security funds) accounted for just over one-half of total health expenditures (3.3 percent of GDP). The bulk of private health expenditure is out-of-pocket (2.5 percent of GDP), whereas private health insurance plays only a small role (0.4 percent of GDP, equivalent to about one-eighth of private health spending).

Public health services were financed from three main sources (WHO (2006)).¹⁴ In the first place, the government finances capital expenditures, wages and salaries, and subsidies to public health facilities from the budget. The social security transfers a negotiated payment to the Ministry of Finance, as payment for medical care received by insured patients, and contributes to some capital spending. Additionally, patients covered by social insurance (and those qualifying for "reduced tariffs") pay a contribution towards the costs of services received, and patients not covered by insurance pay for services at a higher rate.

¹³ The paragraph summarizes the more detailed description by Arfa and Achouri (2008).

¹⁴ Health financing has recently gone through some reforms, which means that the funding of health services over the last few years might reflect structural shifts owing to these reforms. This is an area in which the current report could benefit from feedback from authorities and local experts.

The health reforms that were being implemented from 2007 had three objectives (WHO (2006)):¹⁵ (1) Expanding access to health insurance, to reduce inequities and risk arising from reliance on out-of-pocket payments; (2) improving access to private health providers for patients insured through social insurance; and (3) increasing competition for the public sector through private providers. The key resources reviewed for this report did not capture the outcomes of this reform. Recent trends in health spending point to an increased contribution from social insurance funds, which however appear to replace budgetary resources rather than private health expenditures.

Access to Health Services Across Households

Concern regarding access to health services for poor households and the economic risks associated with large out-of-pocket payments have been cited as motives for the ongoing health reforms, which – among other objectives – aim to improve access and reduce the risks by expanding the coverage of insurance.

The evidence, however, between the intersection of poverty, out-of-pocket spending, and access to health services is weak. To address this issue adequately, it would be necessary to obtain data from the most recent household expenditure survey, which is available in Arabic only and not included in the current “desk” survey. Furthermore, the only Demographic and Health Survey available (MSP and Macro Systems, Inc, (1989)) relates to 1988 and does not differentiate households by economic category.

It appears, however, that the available aggregate data is consistent with views that high out-of-pocket spending results in barriers to access to health services. Household spending on health has increased steeply in recent years, both in absolute terms and relative to household income. Spending on health (category “hygiene et soins”) in household spending has increased from 7 percent of household spending in 1980 to 10.3 percent of household spending in 2005. Combined with the facts that most household spending is out-of-pocket, and that the average share presumably masks very large differences across households, and that within health spending expenditures on “exceptional medical cares” have increased (between 2000 and 2005, according to Arfa and others (2007)), this high level of private health spending points to vulnerabilities and barriers to access among poorer households. Additionally, it has been observed that access to health services differs across regions, and is lower for rural areas (Arfa and others, 2007).

¹⁵ Arfa and Achouri (2008) also discuss ongoing health sector reforms, who focus on the period through 2004.

IV. The National Response to HIV/AIDS

The PNLs was set up in 1987, after the first AIDS case was reported in Tunisia in 1986. It is managed by the Primary Health Care Directorate (Direction des Soins de Santé de Base) at the Ministry of Health,¹⁶ and guided by the National Committee to Fight AIDS (Comité National de Lutte contre le SIDA (CNLS)). In 1998, its mandate was broadened to also cover other sexually transmitted diseases. The national response to HIV/AIDS has been guided by the National Strategic Plan to Fight HIV/AIDS and STIs 2006-2010 (MSP, 2006), which focused on¹⁷ (1) improving the organisation of the national response, and improving the understanding of the dynamics of the epidemic; (2) reducing the risk of HIV transmission; and (3) reducing mortality and morbidity among people living with HIV/AIDS. A new national strategic plan is currently being prepared.

Much of the activities under the national response to HIV/AIDS are geared towards prevention efforts. Contaminated blood supply was a primary source of infection initially, but has played a very small role only since 1987. Much of the activities supported by the Global Fund regard strengthening prevention services and outreach to high-risk groups, including by strengthening NGOs working with these population groups (also see discussion of Global Fund budget, below). Nevertheless, the steep difference between HIV prevalence among risk groups (0.4 percent among female sex workers, 4.8 percent among IDUs, and about 13 percent among men who have sex with men) continues to pose a risk of a further spread of HIV/AIDS among the general population.

Antiretroviral treatment was introduced through the public health system in 2000 (MSP and PNLs, 2010). Treatment is provided free of charge, and financed from the budget of the PNLs (first-line drugs and test kits), the Global Fund (2nd- and 3rd-line drugs), and the general public health budget (human resource costs etc.). The number of people receiving treatment has steadily increased from 114 in 2001 to 412 in 2009 (Mamouri (2010), UNAIDS (2010c)). However, treatment coverage has declined in recent years and currently stood at about 50 percent of estimated need (applying a CD4 eligibility criterion of 350).¹⁸ Most recently, MSP and PNLs (2010) report that 379 people were receiving treatment in mid-2010, corresponding to a treatment coverage rate of only 34 percent. This low coverage rate is achieved even though virtually all people known to be living with HIV/AIDS and requiring treatment reportedly receive it (MSP and PNLs, 2010), pointing to persistent barriers to entry.¹⁹ Drug resistance emerges as an area of concern – according to a recent study, over two-thirds of people receiving treatment included in the study were resistant to at least one type of antiretroviral drugs (MSP and PNLs, 2010).

¹⁶ A discussion of the national response to HIV/AIDS through 2005 is included in Ministry of Health and Country Coordinating Mechanism (2006), and Ministry of Health (2006).

¹⁷ See also the review of the National Strategic Plan 2006-2010 included in MSP and PNLs (2010).

¹⁸ The number of people receiving treatment reported by UNAIDS (2010c) is inconsistent with national data (Maamouri (2010),

¹⁹ The low treatment coverage rate (34 percent) is puzzling when related to the number of people known to live with HIV/AIDS (1,079 in 2009, or 45 percent of people estimated to be living with HIV/AIDS). As the share of people known to be living with HIV/AIDS presumably is higher the longer a person is infected, one would expect that among people requiring treatment, a share larger than the population average is known to be living with HIV/AIDS and receiving treatment.

The Cost of the National Response to HIV/AIDS

Data on the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS are barely available in the public domain. For the national HIV/AIDS program the main sources are PNLS (2005) for spending data through 2004, and MSP (2010) for recent data (Figure 5.1).²⁰ According to these data, spending through the PNLS has increased from TD 0.2 million in the early 1990s to TD 2.6 million in 2002, but declined subsequently and amounted to just over TD 1 million in 2008 and 2009. MSP (2010) also provides a crude breakdown of spending for the year 2008, when 40 percent of the budget was spent on the purchase of test kits, and 60 percent on the purchase of 1st-line antiretroviral drugs.

Figure 7. Available Data on HIV/AIDS Spending

In recent years, however, identified HIV/AIDS spending has been dominated by expenditures supported by the grant from the Global Fund (Figure 5.2). The grant had an overall volume of US\$ 16.2 million (about TD 22 million, applying average exchange rate from mid-2007 to mid-2011), and supported the bulk of identified HIV/AIDS spending in 2008-2010. There is little explicit information on the activities supported by Global Fund spending. According to Global Fund disbursement reports, about 11 percent of total spending through March 2011 supported purchases of pharmaceuticals and other health equipment (including 2nd-line drugs), and 65 percent were passed on to sub-recipients of the grant.

However, the grant proposal to the Global Fund (Ministry of Health and Country Coordinating Mechanism, 2006) provides a more disaggregated breakdown of *budgeted* spending. About one-half (US\$ 8.3 million) of the total requested amount of US\$ 17.4 million was in support of prevention,

²⁰ Berrebeh (2006) also provides a discussion of spending under the national HIV/AIDS program from 1990-2004.

especially among risk groups, capacity building for “NGOs as key actors for prevention among high-risk behaviour groups,” and to “help vulnerable groups to be more willing to seek care for STIs” (all numbers refer to the totals over the 5-year duration of the grant). Other major items included the treatment of opportunistic infections and the management of chronic conditions (US\$ 2.5 million), and investments in surveillance, monitoring, and evaluation (US\$ 3.3 million). Antiretroviral treatment (US\$ 0.4 million) played a subordinate role.

The available data on HIV/AIDS-related spending thus offer only a very superficial and possibly incomplete picture of the financial and fiscal costs of HIV/AIDS in Tunisia. It appears that spending supported by the Global Fund is not included in the accounts of the PNLs (this is plausible not only because spending supported by the Global Fund by far exceeds the budget of the PNLs in recent years, but also as the limited information available suggests that spending financed by the two sources occurs in different areas (e.g., the budget of the PNLs supports first-line antiretroviral drugs, the Global Fund supports the purchase of second-line drugs). If this conclusion is correct, the HIV/AIDS-related spending amounted to about TD 7 million, or 0.01 percent of GDP, in 2009.²¹

Nevertheless, the data suffer from important shortcomings regarding a full understanding of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS. It is not clear to which extent the costs of HIV/AIDS-related services are included in the budgets of the PNLs or spending supported by the Global Fund. For example, while these budgets include items for purchases of first-line (PNLS) and second-line (Global Fund) drugs, it is not clear how the costs of delivering those drugs (health professionals, supply chains) are covered. Similar uncertainties regard the treatment of opportunistic infections and management of chronic conditions, which are included in the Global Fund proposal, but where the data do not identify actual spending, and it is not clear whether the budgeted amounts were based on a full costing.

Additional, the demand for certain services is affected by HIV/AIDS, even though these services are not integrated in the national response to HIV/AIDS. One example for such services is support to orphans and vulnerable children, which are not included in the national response because existing coping mechanisms through families are deemed sufficient (MSP, 2010). Nevertheless, orphans up to age 16 (21 if in education) can claim an orphan pension from the Caisse Nationale de Sécurité Sociale, and 86,183 were receiving one in 2008, at a total cost (excluding administrative costs) of TD35.7 million.²² Judging from the contribution of HIV/AIDS to mortality (0.4 percent among the population of ages 15-59), orphan pensions could therefore add a few hundred thousand TD to the costs of HIV/AIDS.²³

²¹ There are some uncertainties underlying this calculation. The accounting cycle of the Global Fund is not aligned with the fiscal year (which coincides with the calendar year, according to IMF (2010)), and the spending data are reported by the Global Fund in US\$, whereas actual spending occurs in TD. The data were transformed back into TD using the average exchange rate for the respective periods (source: oanda.com). This double transformation – first into US\$, then – only with summary information about the applicable exchange rate – back into TD introduces some scope for error.

²² According to data obtained from the website of the Caisse Nationale de Sécurité Sociale, <http://http://www.cnss.nat.tn>, on January 31, 2012.

²³ The share of “HIV/AIDS” orphans among total orphans could be higher than the contribution of HIV/AIDS to mortality of ages 15-59, because HIV/AIDS deaths disproportionately occur among young adults, and because a disproportionate share of HIV/AIDS orphans are double orphans, but it may be lower if people living with HIV/AIDS have a relatively small number of children.

The (Draft) National Strategic Plan 2012-2016

Note: The summary and discussion of the draft national strategic plan and of the projected costs presented here are based on a preliminary version of the national strategic plan, and are included for drafting purposes, but strictly not for quoting.

The draft National Strategic Plan 2012-2016 is prepared at a time of political transition in Tunisia, and in the context of a changing global environment. The protection of human rights of people living with HIV/AIDS is emphasized as one of its guiding principles, and the plan endorses the vision of “3 Ones” (zero new infections, zero HIV/AIDS deaths, and zero discrimination) spelled out in the UNAIDS 2011-15 strategy (UNAIDS, 2010d).

Table 1. Objectives and Operational Targets of National Strategic Plan 2012-2015

Objectives

- Number of new infections stabilizes below 100 per year.
- Mother-to-child transmission eliminated.
- HIV/AIDS-related mortality reduced by one-half.
- Quality of life of people living with HIV/AIDS comparable to national average.

Operational Targets

- 50 percent of young people and displaced populations, and 20 percent of women at reproductive age adopt attitudes and behaviours which protect them from the risk of HIV infection, and 75 percent of pregnant women at risk have access to PMTCT services.
- 75 percent of sex workers, 75 percent of men who have sex with men, 50 percent of injecting drug users, and 75 percent of prison inmates adopt attitudes and behaviours which protect them from the risk of HIV infection (currently: 51.6 percent, 40.7 percent, 30 percent, and 3 percent, respectively).
- 70 percent of people living with HIV/AIDS receiving care and treatment have access to high-quality management (currently: 49 percent).
- 70 percent of people living with HIV/AIDS benefit from psychosocial support [adapté] (currently: 19 percent).
- The legal framework facilitates universal access in all areas of the response to HIV/AIDS.
- Vulnerable populations, key populations, migrants, and displaced people are able to exercise their rights in all areas of the response to HIV/AIDS.
- Target populations are satisfied that HIV/AIDS interventions respect their human rights.
- Reinforced leadership, coordination, and partnerships.
- National response to HIV/AIDS integrated in health system.
- The monitoring and evaluation system of the national response to HIV/AIDS is fully functional.

Source: Ministère de la Santé Publique and Programme National de Lutte Contre le SIDA et les MST (2012).

The national strategic plan spells out four key outcomes, and a set of operational targets, which are summarized in Table 1. The outcomes framework is supported by a strategy organized in four pillars. The first pillar spells out the strategy to reduce HIV incidence, notably through improved access to prevention services to vulnerable population groups and those with high-risk behaviour. The second pillar focuses on reducing mortality among people living with HIV/AIDS, by improving access to treatment and providing care and support to people living with HIV/AIDS and their environment. The third pillar involves reforms of the legal framework and promotion of human rights, in order to protect the dignity of people living with HIV/AIDS, reduce stigma, and ensure equitable access to treatments and prevention services for all population groups. The fourth pillar concerns capacity building (especially by support to [systèmes communautaires]) and

improving the efficiency of the national response through an improved understanding of the drivers of the epidemic (populations at risk, and modes of transmission).

The draft National Strategic Plan is complemented by cost projections over the next 5 years (which also form the basis of the projections of the costs of the national response HIV/AIDS further below), summarized in Figure 8. The largest share of budgeted spending goes towards the first pillar (HIV prevention), accounting for over one-half of the projected costs of the activities under the National Strategic Plan. Within prevention activities, just over one-half of the budget is allocated to measures targeting high-risk populations (sex workers, injecting drug users, men who have sex with men, and prison inmates), the bulk of the remainder goes towards young adults and prevention of mother-to-child transmission. The cost of care and treatment absorb almost 30 percent of the costs of the National Strategic Plan, the largest item here (70 percent of the costs of care and treatment, and 20 percent of the total costs) is the cost of antiretroviral treatment. The activities under pillar 3, largely regarding the legal framework, do not carry large financial costs (0.4 percent of total). 18 percent of the projected costs support the fourth pillar, and over 90 percent of these funds are assigned to capacity strengthening among NGOs.

Figure 8. Projected Costs of NSP, 2012-16

V. Projected Costs of National Response to HIV/AIDS

As a first step to an analysis of the financial sustainability of the national response to HIV/AIDS, the present section offers projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS, in two steps. First, epidemiological projections are presented, building on the discussion of the state of the epidemic in Section II, and reflecting assumptions and targets contained in the draft National Strategic Plan 2012-16. These epidemiological projections, together with information and assumptions about intended coverage rates of HIV/AIDS-related services and the costs of providing such services, form the basis of the projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS.

Projected Course of Epidemic

The principal challenge in projecting the course of the epidemic over the period covered by the draft National Strategic Plan and beyond is the disconnect between the available *actual data* on the state of the epidemic, and available *estimates* of the state of the epidemic. That there is some discrepancy is unavoidable, as HIV cases are detected only with a lag (and frequently only as the symptoms of AIDS become apparent), and as people living with HIV/AIDS may not be recorded in the official data. For this reason, the number of people reported to be living with HIV/AIDS as of 2009 (1071, see Fig. 1) is much lower than the estimated number of people living with HIV/AIDS (2400, according to UNAIDS (2010a, 2010b, 2010c), see Fig. 2).

This discrepancy is not fully resolved in the draft National Strategic Plan, which makes reference to the estimates prepared by UNAIDS (2010a, 2010b, 2010c) for 2009, but focuses on the reported number of HIV cases. As it is not always clear which numbers or estimates the targets specified in the draft National Strategic Plan refer to, the discrepancy introduces some ambiguities in interpreting the targets spelled out in the National Strategic Plan.

For example, the one of the objectives of the draft National Strategic Plan is to stabilize the number of new HIV infections at less than 100 per year (“nombre de nouvelles infections sera stabilisé à moins de 100 infections par an”). If this number refers to the reported cases, it would be consistent with a scenario in which HIV incidence remains broadly stable. If the number refers to the estimates by UNAIDS, it would imply a drop in HIV incidence by over two-thirds from the 2009 levels, and it is not clear through which measures a decline of this magnitude would be attained.

Similarly, the draft National Strategic Plan targets an increase in the number of people receiving antiretroviral treatment from 412 to 590, and an increase in the number of patients receiving appropriate care (“70% de PVVIH attendues sont correctement pris en charge (situation actuelle estimée : 49%)”). At the same time, the draft National Strategic Plan includes activities to reduce barriers in access to HIV/AIDS services (presumably leading to an increase in the share of people living with HIV/AIDS seeking treatment and care). On the other hand, the projections of the need for treatment, building on the UNAIDS estimates, suggest that well over a 1,000 people will become eligible for treatment over the 2012-2016 period. If this is the case, the targeted increase in the number of people receiving treatment would imply a decline in the treatment coverage rate.

For these reasons, it will be urgently necessary to clarify the assumptions underlying the targets and objectives (and therefore the cost estimates) included in the draft National Strategic Plan. The analysis offered here – based largely on public sources – may therefore be out of line with the projections used by the authorities.

The projections offered below are building on the estimates prepared by UNAIDS (2010a, 2010b, 2010c). These estimates implied a steep increase in HIV incidence, rising from 229 in 2005 to 350 among adults in 2009. As a working assumptions, the projections are based on the assumption that the number of new infections among adults declines to 200 annually over the 2012-2016 period, and

remains at that level thereafter (as the population continues to grow, this implies a slow continuing decline in the HIV incidence rate).

Regarding the treatment coverage rate, the projections are based on the assumption that 80 percent of people living with HIV/AIDS are seeking care and treatment through the public health system. Judging from the data on reported cases and the corresponding estimates, it appears that this rate would require an increase in the share of people living with HIV/AIDS reached by the public health system. Of these, it is assumed that 70 percent receive the required treatment (in line with the objectives of the draft National Strategic Plan. Again, it should be stressed that these assumptions are working hypotheses, which would need to be validated or corrected by the authorities. The

Figure 8. People Living with HIV/AIDS, Ages 15+, 2010-2030

Figure 8 summarizes the projections of the course of the epidemic, based on these assumptions and the epidemiological model described in the appendix. The number of adults living with HIV/AIDS is projected to increase steeply from about 2,500 in 2011 to 3,000 in 2015, but remain at or slowly decline from that level. The composition of the population living with HIV/AIDS reflects the main drivers of the number of people living with HIV/AIDS – while the number of people not deemed eligible for treatment declines from 1,600 in 2011 to 1,200 in 2030, increased access to treatment and the longer survival of people receiving treatment result in a steep increase in the number of people receiving treatment, from about 400 in 2010 to 1,200 in 2020, and 1,600 in 2030.

It is important to keep in mind that the scenario described in Fig. 8 is built on the assumption of a steep decline in HIV incidence over the course of the draft National Strategic Plan 2012-16. If this decline does not materialize, but HIV incidence remains at its 2011 level, the number of people living with HIV/AIDS would increase to 4,000 by 2020, and 4,600 by 2030, and the number of people receiving treatment would reach 1,400 by 2020, and increase further to over 2,000 by 2030.

Projected Costs of the National Response to HIV/AIDS

The projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS build on three data sources. (1) The projections of the course of the epidemic (which also incorporate some assumptions on the objectives of the national response), above; (2) the preliminary costing of the National Strategic Plan 2012-16; and – where the costing does not clearly identify the costs of certain activities – supplementary information, including budget information from Tunisia and cross-country evidence.

The projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS are summarized in Fig. 9. As the projections are largely based on the costing of the draft National Strategic Plan 2012-16, which is well documented above and in the source documents, it is not necessary to discuss the assumptions underlying the projections in detail here. Nevertheless, there are some noticeable differences to the costing of the draft National Strategic Plan. The most important difference regards the costs of treatment. As observed earlier, it was not possible to reconcile the objectives of the National Strategic Plan in terms of coverage rates, the targeted numbers of people receiving treatment, and the estimates of the course of the epidemic prepared by UNAIDS. For this reason, the estimates of people

receiving treatment in the present paper are higher than in the draft costing of the National Strategic Plan (rising from TD 2.0 million in 2012 to TD 3.3 million in 2016, instead of an increase from TD 1.8 million to TD 2.4 million). Second, an allowance for the cost of orphan pensions attributable to HIV/AIDS was included in the costs (subsumed under “treatment, care, and support”). Third, the costing of the National Strategic Plan does not provide a clear account of the costs of the management of the program, and an allowance for administrative expenses equivalent to 10 percent of the costs (excluding overhead) was included in the projections. Some open questions at the time of writing included the costing of prevention of mother-to-child transmission, and the question to which extent HIV/AIDS-related health services were included in the costing. (This report was prepared as a basis for discussion before an envisaged visit to Tunisia, where some of the open questions could easily be resolved.)

Figure 9 summarizes the projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS. The costs rise steeply initially, owing to early investments in capacity strengthening of civil society groups [correctly translated?] and the scaling-up of treatment. While the costs of prevention interventions (corresponding to axis one of the National Strategic Plan) are the largest component of the costs initially, the costs of treatment, care, and support eventually dominate the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS, with costs rising from TD 3 million (one-quarter of the total cost) in 2012 to TD 7.7 million (43 percent of the total costs) in 2030. This increase in costs reflects the growing number of people receiving treatment, as documented above.

Overall, the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS come out at TD 12.7 million in 2012, rising to TD 14.3 million by 2016, and TD 18.0 million in 2030 (all in constant prices).²⁴ While the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS increase steadily in this scenario, it should be noted that this scenario is built on the assumption of a steep decline in HIV incidence – if HIV incidence remains at the level estimated by UNAIDS for 2009 (about 350 infections annually), then the costs increase more steeply, to TD 14.5 million by 2016, and TD 21.5 million in 2030 (Figure 10), with costs of treatment, care and support accounting for one-half of the total costs.

²⁴ For the reasons indicated, this is somewhat higher than the projected costs of the National Strategic Plan, which add up to TD x million in 2012, and TD z million in 2016.

VI. HIV Incidence and the Costs of the National Response to HIV/AIDS

On one hand it is rather obvious that the decline in HIV incidence assumed in the projections should result in a slowdown in the costs of the national response further out. However, the assumed drop in HIV incidence is large – a decline from around 350 infections annually to 200 infections annually between 2012 and 2016, sustained afterwards. From this perspective, the slowdown in the costs of the national response (spending at TD 18.0 million in 2030 rather than TD 21.5 million) appears very small. Furthermore, if one takes into account that the assumed decline in HIV incidence reflects higher investments in prevention efforts and capacity building, which would need to be taken out for a proper comparison, it is not obvious which one of the two scenarios carries the higher financial costs over the projection period.

However, it also appears that the cost comparison understates the differences in the financial costs between the scenarios – at the end of the projection period, the accumulated number of infections between 2012 and 2030 is reduced by 2,200, and the number of people living with HIV/AIDS in 2030 stands at 3,000, whereas it would rise to 4,700 without a decline in HIV incidence. These achievements are immediately valuable in terms of improved health outcomes. However, they are also relevant for an understanding of the financial consequences of the national response to HIV/AIDS – at the end of the projection period, the country faces a much reduced cost of serving the needs of people living with HIV/AIDS alive at that state (and a much reduced cost of anticipated future infections).

The present section outlines how to utilize the epidemiological and costing framework described above can be used to better inform policy choices regarding the financial dimension of alternative HIV/AIDS policies (alongside with the intended health outcomes). This is achieved in two steps. First, the costs caused by an individual HIV infection are estimated. Second, these estimates are used to assess the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS, linking the overall costs to the underlying HIV incidence.

The costs caused by an individual adult infection are summarized in Figure 11. It has been estimated by adding one HIV infection in 2010, and calculating the resulting increase in the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS.²⁵ For each year, the expected costs reflect the weighted

²⁵ Costs differ somewhat between males and females, owing to different survival probabilities and the potential costs of mother-to-child-transmission. The estimate shown is a weighted average of the costs of a male and a female HIV infection, respectively.

probability of being in a certain state of the epidemic, the coverage of HIV/AIDS-related services pertaining to this state, and the assumption on unit costs. The expected costs rise to about TD 1,600 annually over the first 10 years following an HIV infection, largely reflecting the increasing likelihood that the individual will require and – depending on the treatment coverage rate – receive first-line treatment. The expected costs then decline slowly, reflecting both transition to more expensive types of treatment and increased mortality among people living with HIV/AIDS.

Overall, the expected costs incurred by one additional infection come out at TD 22,500, equivalent to about US\$ 16,000, or three times GDP per capita. This is the amount that the government would have to pay (applying an interest rate of 3 percent) at the time of infection to cover the expected costs of HIV/AIDS-related services caused by this infection.

This insight can also be used to assess the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS, and how the financial costs change in response to a decline or increase in HIV incidence. Rather than tracking the consequences of reduced infections for the costs of the HIV/AIDS program over very long time periods – Figure 11 suggests that 40 years would be an appropriate time frame – the costs of treatment, care, and support, and any other costs which are directly affected by HIV incidence – are attributed to the time the infection occurs.

The costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS on a cash basis (i.e., in terms of current HIV/AIDS-related expenditures) and on a commitment basis (based on spending commitments as a consequence of new HIV infections) are compared in Figure 12. Actual spending increases steeply at the beginning of the period covered by the draft National Strategic Plan 2012-2016, reflecting primarily some investments in capacities, increasing coverage of HIV/AIDS services, and the build-up in the number of

people receiving treatment. The costs incurred by new infections, however, decline from TD 8 million in 2011 to TD 5 million in 2016, and remain at about that level.

If HIV incidence had remained at its 2011 level, the costs incurred by new infections would have increased from TD 8 million to about TD 9 million by 2018, slowly increasing to TD 9.5 million after this. The assumed decline in HIV incidence thus releases fiscal space equivalent to TD 4 million annually by the end of the period covered by the National Strategic Plan. To evaluate the investments in HIV prevention included in the National Strategic Plan, it would be necessary – in addition to the intended health outcomes – to take into account this financial saving, so that spending decisions are made on the basis of the net costs of an intervention (i.e., net of the financial savings).

There are two areas in which the analysis could be taken further, but which would require more data and a more substantial modelling effort. One issue that has not been addressed in the discussion so far is the difference between immediate impacts of HIV/AIDS interventions, and population effects. As HIV/AIDS is a communicable disease, an additional infection does have implications for the further course of disease. Taking into account that an HIV-positive individual may pass on the virus further, the costs incurred directly by an additional infection may underestimate its financial consequences, as they do not account for the expected costs of further infections. This aspect is particularly important for assessing the financial dimension for infections targeting risk groups, which are motivated by a perception that the risk of passing on the virus among these groups is highest. The other issue regards the impact of HIV/AIDS interventions. Here, the analysis could go a step further and consider some of the determinants of infections, and connect the analysis closer to the operational targets of the national response to HIV/AIDS.

At this stage, please note once more that these calculations are based on a very crude analysis, and have not been discussed with authorities or other knowledgeable people on the ground. Some of the underlying assumptions are therefore very preliminary based on incomplete information, and have not been validated in any form.

VII. Sustainability of the National Response to HIV/AIDS

In Tunisia, the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS are small from a macroeconomic perspective, or seen against the scale of public expenditures overall. The critical issue for the financial sustainability of the national response to HIV/AIDS is therefore not whether the national response to HIV/AIDS can be financed, but whether the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS are reasonable when measured against the programs contributions to health outcomes or other government objectives.

The analysis above suggests that the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS amount to about TD 12.7 million in 2012, rising to TD 18.0 by 2030 (or TD 21.5 if the assumed decline in HIV incidence does not materialize). For 2012, this means that the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS are equivalent to 0.02 percent of GDP, 0.07 percent of public expenditures,²⁶ or 0.6 percent of public health expenditures. While the costs are projected to increase over the coming years, economic capacities (GDP, fiscal revenues) will presumably expand, too. Overall, the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS increase at an average rate of 2.0 percent annually (or 3.0 percent if the assumed decline in HIV incidence does not materialize). Either of these rates are lower than historical rates of economic growth (which averaged 4.4 percent annually between 2000 and 2010, according to IMF (2011)), suggesting that the burden of financing the national response to HIV/AIDS, relative to domestic resources, will decline over the projection period.

²⁶ Fiscal data were taken from IMF (2010).

Another aspect of the sustainability of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS regards the weight of HIV/AIDS-related spending in public expenditures, in light of the impact of the epidemic and other objectives of public policy. This is an issue that is much beyond the scope of the present study. The estimates of the contribution of HIV/AIDS to the burden of disease offer some pointers – WHO (2011) estimates that HIV/AIDS caused one in 918 (or 0.1 percent of) deaths nationally in 2008, and one in 236 deaths (or 0.4 percent) among the population of ages 15-59.

Simply comparing the share of HIV/AIDS in public health spending (0.6 percent) to the burden of disease suggests that HIV/AIDS takes a disproportionate share of public resources.²⁷ However, to assess whether HIV/AIDS spending is too high relative to other public health priorities, comparing HIV/AIDS spending to average health spending can be misleading, as HIV/AIDS could be compared with a number of low-cost health interventions, as well as more expensive interventions provided through public health services. For the sustainability of HIV/AIDS spending it is critical that the costs of HIV/AIDS interventions are below the costs (per life year gained, or death averted) of the more expensive treatments provided through the public health system (i.e., whether the costs of HIV/AIDS interventions are “intra-marginal”). One pointer in this direction is the cost of antiretroviral treatment (between TD 2,600 and TD 8,000, according to the draft costing of the National Strategic Plan).²⁸ These costs correspond to between 40 percent of GDP per capita and 130 percent of GDP per capita (for 3rd-line therapy). From this comparison it appears that at least the costs of first- and second-line antiretroviral therapy are clearly within the range that would normally be offered through the public health system. In case of third-line therapy, more information on the Tunisian health system and the more expensive services provided through it would be required.

A focus on treatment, as in the previous paragraph, misses out on important aspects of HIV/AIDS and the response to the epidemic. From a public health perspective, one of the defining aspects of HIV/AIDS is the fact that it is a communicable and sexually transmitted disease. This means that the impact of HIV interventions is subject to externalities – the beneficiaries of HIV/AIDS interventions are not only (in some cases, not even mainly) the individuals and groups targeted by the intervention, but wider population groups whose risk of contracting HIV is reduced. Where such externalities are important, the private provision of health services is not sufficient. From this perspective, a disproportionate role of the public sector in providing HIV/AIDS-related services is appropriate.

In evaluating the role of the public sector in the provision of HIV/AIDS-related services (and of health services generally), distributional concerns are also relevant. HIV/AIDS is a long-term medical condition, the treatment of which is relatively expensive. Both these aspects mean that HIV/AIDS may exacerbate differences in access to care and in the economic consequences of disease across population groups. This issue, however, is beyond the scope of the current analysis (but could become relevant if health spending data across households become available).

In sum, whether considering the level of HIV/AIDS-related spending from the perspective of the sustainability of public finance, or across competing demands for public resources, it appears that the national response to HIV/AIDS is financially sustainable, even if external financing dries up. In this situation, and also in light of the relatively high level of GDP per capita, the case for accessing external financing rests on two conditions: (1) knowledge transfer, and (2) institutional constraints, and both play a role in the draft National Strategic Plan 2012-16.

²⁷ There are some important shortcomings to using the WHO’s estimates of the burden of disease for comparisons with health spending. Most importantly, the estimates give the burden of disease *after* the impact of interventions, and are therefore not a good measure of the disease environment. Any such comparisons should therefore be treated with caution and judgement.

²⁸ It is not clear whether these estimates are based on a full costing of treatment. This will need to be resolved here and in the projections of the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS.

One of the priorities spelled out in the draft National Strategic Plan is gaining efficiency gains through an improved understanding of the epidemiology of HIV/AIDS in Tunisia. In addition to national efforts, the planning of the national response of HIV/AIDS has benefitted from efforts to share the international experience (see, for example, Abu-Raddad and others (2010a, 2010b), and organisations like UNAIDS, the WHO, or UNAIDS continue to play an important role in this area.

Another priority of the draft National Strategic Plan, to which a substantial share of funding is allocated to, is capacity building among NGOs and civil society. In this area, external funding could usefully complement domestic public resources, especially in areas where stigma-related issues constrain the effectiveness of the public sector in delivering services.

VIII. Conclusions and Outlook

The paper is shared in a preliminary version to solicit feedback, sharpen the thrust of the analysis, and align it with policy questions currently under discussion regarding the preparation of the new National Strategic Plan 2012-2016. At this stage, the analysis is largely based on documents available in the public domain, and has not received feedback from the authorities. Additionally, the analysis would require guidance on the state of HIV/AIDS or the costs of the national response, as some of the evidence in the public domain is ambiguous.

Nevertheless, there are some broad messages coming out of this preliminary analysis, including the following:

- The projected costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS rise from TD 12.7 million in 2012 to TD 18 million by 2030.
- The cost of the national response to HIV/AIDS does not raise issues of fiscal sustainability – it is estimated at 0.02 percent of GDP or 0.07 percent of government spending. While the costs are projected to increase, they will probably do so more slowly than GDP.
- The costs incurred by an additional HIV infection (or saved by an infection prevented) are estimated at 3 times GDP per capita.
- Spending on HIV/AIDS does not seem out of line with overall public health spending and the burden of disease. The costs at least of first- and second-line treatment seem to be well within the range normally supported by public health spending.

Steps that would be necessary to validate the estimates or take the analysis further include:

- Validate the assumptions underlying the epidemiological projections, including the interpretation of the course of the epidemic.
- Validate the costing assumptions. Costs of treatment seem high by international standards, e.g., against the costs budgeted by other middle-income countries. Clarify why this is the case.
- Clarify scope of spending under national response to HIV/AIDS.
- Integrating findings from modes-of-transmission study in analysis, to obtain better estimates of the costs incurred by additional infections (including increased risk of onward infections).
- Where possible, provide a more explicit analysis of cost-effectiveness of prevention measures. The data situation is very difficult here, but it may be possible to combine data on the costs and the effectiveness of prevention measures with epidemiological information and the economic analysis of the costs of the HIV/AIDS program.

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Appendix: Epidemiological Framework

The analysis offered in this report combines three building blocks: (1) an epidemiological model, (2) a costing framework for projecting the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS, and (3) an economic framework to calibrate the costs incurred by new infections, which is also used to link the costs of the national HIV/AIDS program to the HIV infections which ultimately cause the demand for HIV/AIDS-related services.

In the appendix, we offer some more detail on the epidemiological framework, and on the tools applied in the analysis of the spending commitments incurred by new HIV infections.

Epidemiological Framework

The epidemiological framework is integrated in the economic (spreadsheet-based) framework, allowing an integrated analysis of the progression of the disease, the demand of HIV/AIDS-related services, and the costs of the national response to HIV/AIDS. For this purpose, an epidemiological framework was calibrated that reproduces the estimates provided by the Ministry of Health which, in turn, build on the analysis summarized by Duncan and others (2010) using the Spectrum model.

The structure of the epidemiological module is summarized in Figure 1. As an HIV infection occurs, adults move from state “no HIV” to “HIV asymptomatic.” Eventually, people living with HIV/AIDS reach treatment need. The model distinguishes treatment need applying a CD4 count of 350 and of 200, respectively, and can accommodate transitions to treatment at either stage. (For the projections, it is assumed that treatment commences at a CD4 count of 350.)

As individuals reach the stage “treatment need,” they are sorted into those receiving 1st-line treatment, and “unmet need” (from where the next stage is “premature death”). From 1st-line treatment, individuals eventually proceed to treatment failure, and then either to 2nd-line treatment or to “premature death.” From 2nd-line treatment, individuals eventually progress to treatment failure and premature death. To estimate the impact of HIV/AIDS on mortality on the population level, it is important to take into account that people who have died for HIV/AIDS-related reasons would eventually die otherwise. For this reason, individuals who have died prematurely eventually progress to counterfactual death. Another, less fully developed aspect of the model is the impact of HIV/AIDS on the young population, where our model yields estimates of the number of orphans and of children living with HIV/AIDS.

Specifically, the transitions between the states are governed by the following assumptions:

- The transition from HIV infection to eligibility for treatment at a CD4 count of 350 is based on a Weibull distribution, with a mean transition time of 6.2 years for males, and 6.6 years for females.²⁹ From this point, transition to eligibility for treatment at a CD4 count of 200 takes another 3 years (again based on a Weibull distribution)). In the absence of treatment, death occurs on average 3 years after reaching a CD 4 count of 200.
- The model can accommodate treatment initiation at a CD4 count of 350 or 200 (or a combination of the two possibilities). For individuals initiating 1st-line treatment at a CD4 count of 350, transition to 2nd-line treatment need takes 9 years, for individuals who start at a CD4 count of 200, it is 3 years. Unless they receive 2nd-line treatment, death occurs on average 4.6 years after reaching 2nd-line treatment need.
- For individuals receiving 2nd-line treatment, death occurs after about 9 years (as the analysis presented here does not account for further treatment options, it does not need to identify the number of people for whom 2nd-line treatment fails).
- Through 2009, the number of people initiating treatment is based on actual data on the stock of people receiving ART. From 2010 to 2012, 50 percent of people newly requiring treatment

²⁹ In the data provided by the MoH, 14 percent of people living with HIV/AIDS do not make the transition to treatment need. It was not possible so far to clarify whether this reflects an allowance for non-HIV deaths or other reasons.

are assumed to receive it. This rate increases to 54 percent between 2012 and 2016, and remains at that level.

- 70 percent of people receiving first-line treatment eventually move on to second-line treatment.
- For new infections at age 0 (the model does not differentiate between infections before, at, or after birth), it is assumed that the probability of mother-to-child transmission is 34 percent, and that it is reduced by three-quarters through PMTCT, and about 90 percent if the mother is on regular ART.
- The model does not differentiate young people by sex. Transition to treatment need follows a Weibull distribution with a mean of 2.4 years. For children not receiving treatment, transition to death is determined by a Weibull distribution and occurs on average 5.1 years after occurrence of treatment need. For children receiving treatment, the transition to death occurs on average 12.5 years after encountering treatment need.
- The number of orphans is estimated and projected based on a module that builds on male and female adult mortality, and the survival probabilities of children (depending on treatment access).